

Terraforming and Constructing Habitats:

A Chart's Presentation

(The numbers and data presented in this table are approximations)

Nr.	Territory	Surface Area compared to Earth	Period of Time	Number of (potentially) hosted people	Company (Ndoni Advanced Robotics) N.A.R	Number of robots and machinery involved in the process of creating habitats
1.	Mars	0.38	23 rd Century	2.5B+	N.A.R	70M+
2.	Saturn	83	24 th -25 th	600B+	N.A.R	120B+
3.	Jupiter	120	27 th -30 th	900B+	N.A.R	350B+
4.	Solar System	Unspecified	27 th -34 th	10-50T+	N.A.R	500B+
5.	Milky Way galaxy	Unspecified	400k-1m (year)	Unspecified (All creatures who have ever lived on Earth, both Human and Non-Human)	N.A.R	1 Quintillion -1 Septillion

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